

Unjustifiable Waste: An Empirical Study of Repeated Builds During Code Review

APPENDIX

This document is an online appendix for “Unjustifiable Waste: An Empirical Study of Repeated Builds During Code Review”. This document is a summary of the survey response.

TABLE 1
Demographics of survey participants

Role	Contributor	4
	Reviewer	0
	Contributor & Reviewer	20
Years of Experience	Less than 3 years	2
	3-5 years	6
	More than 5 years	16

TABLE 2
Perception of handling test failures

Q1. Frequency of invoking a recheck	Never	0 (0%)
	Rarely	10 (42%)
	Sometimes	10 (42%)
	Often	4 (16%)
	Always	0 (0%)
Q2-a. Awareness of official guidelines	Yes	19 (79%)
	No	5 (21%)
Q3. Have own workflow to handle failures	Yes	13 (54%)
	No	11 (46%)
Q4. Any oversight regarding the recheck	Yes	6 (25%)
	No	18 (75%)

TABLE 3
Q2-b. Perception of practicalness of official guidelines

(i) Examine the logs of the jobs that failed.	24 (100%)
(ii) Try whenever possible to reproduce the failure locally.	20 (83%)
(iii) Look for some indication of what went wrong.	15 (63%)
(iv) Recheck bug #XXXXXXX to a known problem that is being worked.	14 (58%)
(v) Recheck with a reason of “Not sure what failed, rechecking to get another data point”.	13 (54%)
(vi) Reach out (via the mailing list or IRC) to the project team.	9 (38%)
(vii) Open a bug against the project and use that for your recheck.	6 (25%)

TABLE 4
Feedback on our findings (RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3)

RQ	Observation	Aware with experience	Aware without experience	Unaware
RQ1	O1: Change sets are often rechecked after the CI jobs failed (more than 50% of cases).	20 (83%)	1 (4%)	3 (13%)
	O2: On average, a patch set with build failures invoked a recheck twice.	20 (83%)	2 (8%)	2 (8%)
RQ2	O3: CI build outcomes do not often change after the recheck (42% of cases).	13 (54%)	2 (8%)	8 (33%)
	O4: Integration test jobs are more likely to change the build outcomes after recheck has been invoked (when compared to functional, unit and other test jobs).	16 (67%)	1 (4%)	6 (25%)
RQ3	Q5: Much additional computation time is spent (700%) on recheck builds. Furthermore, a change set with rechecks takes much longer (2,200%) to be reviewed when compared to the ones with no rechecks.	16 (67%)	1 (4%)	6 (25%)